

greene

**SINGLE-GRAIN
RE-ENGINEERED
ND-FE-B PERMANENT
MAGNETS**

Funded by
the European Union

The GREENE Project aims to push the boundaries of material science by re-engineering rare earth permanent magnets to become more resource-efficient, whilst offering significant improvements to magnetic performance.

€8 Mio
EU Funding (Horizon Europe)

15 Partners
from 10 European Countries

4 Years
(1st June 2024 until
31st May 2028)

This flyer is made of plantable seed paper.

Partners

Universiteit
Leiden
The Netherlands

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

University for
Continuing
Education Krems

TECHNISCHE
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CONNECT

in GREENE Project

www.greene-project.eu